

The Effect of Brand Image, E-Service Quality, and Customer Value on Decisions to Use Traveloka in Semarang

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ABSTRACT: Traveloka's existence in Indonesia makes it one of the major online travel agents that are in demand by the Indonesian people to fulfill their travel needs. However, in the last few years there has been a tendency to decrease in sales as indicated by data on the decrease in the percentage of sales in 2016-2020. This study aims to determine the effect of brand image, e-service quality, and customer value on purchasing decisions at Traveloka online travel agents. This type of research is explanatory research with sampling using non-probability sampling technique. Data collection is done by using google form. The sample used is 100 respondents who have used purchases at Traveloka online travel agents in Semarang City. This research uses validity test, reliability test, relation coefficient, coefficient of determination, simple regression, multiple regression, t-test significance, and f-test supported by SPSS. The results obtained in this study are brand image, e- service quality, and customer value, which individually or collectively affect purchasing decisions at Traveloka online travel agents. Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, the researchers suggest Traveloka to improve the platform design, optimize services for Traveloka users' complaints and provide a fast and personalized response. Companies are advised to provide training, direction, and attention to customer service in order to provide the best service. In addition, it is recommended to improve service quality intensively so that the benefits (results) obtained by buyers/users are in accordance with the effort and costs incurred, evaluate customer experience, and optimize the recommendation feature.

KEYWORDS: Brand Image; Customer Value; E-Service Quality; Purchase Decision.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry in Indonesia today has a fairly rapid growth. This situation can be seen from the increasing number of online travel agents. Online Travel Agent (OTA) is a site that facilitates users in completing travel needs, including airline tickets, hotels, trains, buses, car rentals, and other tourist activities so that consumers do not need to go to ticket counter to order tickets or hotel reservations. It is now more effective and efficient. More and more consumers are now turning to OTAs to buy tickets or hotel reservations. This is because it allows buyers/users to easily search for travel products by reading reviews of other buyers/users, comparing prices and benefits.

The existence of online travel agents makes it easier for consumers who want to travel so that all their traveling needs become easier, more practical, and users can find out the information needed about their trip correctly. This situation certainly requires service providers to continuously innovate to offer superior travel products according to the needs of the Indonesian people. Every service provider must be able to learn how buyers/users make purchasing decisions and what factors can influence consumer behavior when making purchasing decisions for travel products. Lu, Zeng, & Fan (in Hidayanto et al., 2007) show that if individuals are involved in e-commerce activities, individuals must take into account the high level of risk and uncertainty associated with opportunistic behavior from other parties, which in this context is aimed at on Traveloka as an online travel agent.

Furthermore, the tight competition in online travel agents has caused the percentage of Traveloka's Top Brand Index (TBI) in 2016-2020 to tend to decrease (topbrand-award.com accessed on June 1, 2021). The index, which tends to decrease, indicates that purchasing decisions at Traveloka have also decreased. This is based on TBI measurement based on three parameters, namely mind share, market share, and commitment share. The size of the index can also identify the image of Traveloka itself, then it can influence potential buyers/users in purchasing travel products at Traveloka.

In addition to the percentage of TBI which tends to decrease, researchers also found a number of negative reviews related to Traveloka, both on the Google Play Store and on Traveloka's own social media. Most Traveloka users complain about the quality

of service when accessing Traveloka (e-service quality) and the comparison of the utility obtained with the costs incurred (customer value).

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Based on the background explanation above, there are still some problems faced by the company. In 2016-2020 Traveloka's purchasing decisions tend to decrease. This is known based on Top Brand Index (TBI) data for the category of online flight and travel booking sites from 2016 to 2020, which shows that the numbers tend to decrease. Brand Image, E-Service Quality, and Customer Value are suspected as factors that can influence the purchase decision. Further, the formulation of the problem in this study are:

1. Is there any influence of brand image on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City?
2. Is there any influence of e-service quality on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Marketing behavior

Consumer behavior is defined as the study of the pattern of actions of a person or group in considering, buying, using products or services, ideas, or experiences to fulfill their needs and desires (Kotler and Keller, 2016).

Purchase decision

Kotler and Keller (2016) define that purchasing decisions are the stage of consumer evaluation of creating brand preferences in selection and may also form intentions to buy a brand that is most desired.

Marketing

Kotler and Keller (2016) say that marketing is the process of individuals or groups getting what they want through creating, offering, and exchanging products/services with others.

Brand image

According to Kotler (2000) brand image is a set of beliefs, ideas, and impressions held by individuals or groups of a brand.

Electronic Service Quality (E-Service Quality)

According to Zeithaml et al. (2009) e-service quality is an electronic service that is run to make it easier for consumers to buy and deliver products or services effectively and efficiently.

Customer Value

According to Sweeney and Soutar (2001:204) customer value is the overall evaluation of consumers regarding the utility of a product that is based on an understanding of what is obtained and what is shared.

Hypotheses

The hypothesis is a temporary answer to the formulation of the problem in a study, in which the formulation of the problem in a study has been confirmed in the form of a question. The hypothesis is called temporary because the answers or responses submitted are only based on theory (Sugiyono, 2013: 64). Based on the formulation of the hypothesis in the research that has been arranged, the model of the hypothesis is:

H1: It is assumed that there is a positive influence between brand image on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City.

H2: It is assumed that there is a positive influence between e-service quality on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City.

H3: It is assumed that there is a positive influence between customer value on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City.

H4: It is assumed that there is a positive influence between brand image, e-service quality, and customer value on the decision to use Traveloka services in Semarang City.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses the type of explanatory research with a quantitative approach. Explanatory research is research to find an explanation of the correlation between variables in research and to know the existence of the influence between variables in addition to testing the hypothesis that was formulated initially (Sugiyono, 2006). The population that will be used by the researcher is Traveloka users in Semarang City, whose number is not identified. Based on this population, the sampling refers to the theory of Cooper and Emory (1996), which appoints 100 Traveloka users in the city of Semarang.

The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with purposive sampling. The research instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The scoring in the research questionnaire uses a Likert scale. The analytical methods used are validity test, reliability test, correlation coefficient test, multiple correlation test, coefficient of determination test, determination test (R²), simple regression analysis, multiple regression analysis, t test, and F test.

RESULTS

Table 1. Brand Image Correlation Test Results on Purchase Decisions

		Brand image	Purchase decision
Brand image	Pearson correlation	1	.664**
	Sig. (-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Purchase decision	Pearson correlation	.664**	1
	Sig. (-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

**correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 1, it is known that the value of the correlation coefficient of the two variables is 0.664. The correlation coefficient value of 0.664 is in the range of 0.60 - 0.799 so it can be interpreted that between the brand image variables and purchasing decisions there is a strong correlation level or level of relationship. So, if there is an increase or decrease in the brand image variable on the respondent's perception, it can have an impact on the purchasing decision variable.

Table 2. E-Service Quality Correlation Test Results on Purchase Decisions

		E-Service Quality	Purchase decision
E-Service Quality	Pearson correlation	1	.777**
	Sig. (-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Purchase decision	Pearson correlation	.777**	1
	Sig. (-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

**correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 2, it is known that the value of the correlation coefficient of the two variables is 0.777. The correlation coefficient value of 0.777 is in the range of 0.60 - 0.799, so it means that between the variables of e-service quality and purchasing decisions there is a strong correlation. If there is an increase or decrease in the e-service quality variable on respondents' perceptions, it can have an impact on the purchasing decision variable.

Table 3. Customer Value Correlation Test Results on Purchase Decisions

Correlations		E-Service Quality	Purchase decision
E-Service Quality	Pearson correlation	1	.719**
	Sig. (-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Purchase decision	Pearson correlation	.719**	1
	Sig. (-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

**correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 3, it is known that the value of the correlation coefficient of the two variables is 0.719. The correlation coefficient value of 0.719 is in the range of 0.60 - 0.799, so it means that the customer value variable and purchasing decisions have a strong correlation. If there is an increase or decrease in the customer value variable on the respondent's perception, it can have an impact on the purchasing decision variable.

Table 4. Test Results of Brand Image Determination Coefficient on Purchase Decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.664 ^a	.441	.436	2.003

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 4, it is known that the coefficient of determination of brand image on purchasing decisions is 0.441 or 44.1%.

Table 5. Test Results of E-Service Quality Determination Coefficient on Purchase Decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.777 ^a	.603	.599	1.689

a. Predictors: (Constant), eService Quality

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 5, it is known that the coefficient of determination of e-service quality on purchasing decision is 0.603 or 60.3%.

Table 6. Test Results of Customer Value Determination Coefficient on Purchase Decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.719 ^a	.517	.512	1.863

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Value

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 6, it is known that the coefficient of determination of e-service quality on purchasing decisions is 0.517 or 51.7%.

Table 7. Test Results of Brand Image, eService Quality, Customer Value Determination Coefficient on Purchase Decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.813 ^a	.662	.651	1.575

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image, E-Service Quality, Customer Value

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 7, it is known that the coefficient of determination of brand image, e-service quality, and customer value on purchasing decisions is 0.662 or 66.2%.

Table 8. The Simple Regression Test Result of Brand Image on Purchase Decisions

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	5.835	1.735		3.363	.001
	Brand image	.465	.053	.664	8.800	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 8, the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so that the brand image variable (X1) has a positive influence on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The regression coefficient for the brand image variable (X1) is 0.465 with a constant value of 5.835.

Table 9. The Simple Regression Test Result of eService Quality on Purchase Decisions

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	5.381	1.291		4.168	.000
	eService Quality	.418	.034	.777	12.201	.000

a. Dependent Variable: eService Quality

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 9, the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so that the e-service quality variable (X2) has a positive influence on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The regression coefficient for the variable e-service quality (X2) is 0.418 with a constant value of 5.381.

Table 10. The Simple Regression Test Result of Customer Value on Purchase Decisions

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	7.702	1.312		5.869	.000
	Customer Value	.466	.046	.719	10.236	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Value

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 10, the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so the customer value variable (X3) has a positive influence on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The regression coefficient for the brand image variable (X1) is 0.466 with a constant value of 7.702.

Table 11. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results of Brand Image, E-Service Quality, and Customer Value on Purchase Decisions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.808	1.417		1.981	.050
	Brand Image	.135	.059	.493	2.286	.024
	eService Quality	.234	.055	.435	4.240	.000
	Customer Value	.176	.060	.272	2.952	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Value

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on Table 11, a constant value of 2.808 is obtained where if there are no brand image, e-service quality, and customer value variables, the magnitude of the perception of the purchase decision is 2.808. The regression coefficient for the brand image variable (X1) is 0.135, e-service quality (X2) is 0.234, and customer value (X3) is 0.176 so it is said that brand image (X1) is 0.135, e-service quality (X2) is 0.234, and customer value (X3) can have a positive influence on purchasing decisions (Y).

HYPOTHESES TESTING

t-test

The t-count of the brand image variable is 8.800. Furthermore, the value of the t-table is searched through the previous df (degree of freedom), so that $df = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$ is obtained. The df is obtained as much as 98, then if observed through t-one tailed using 5% significance, the value will be obtained t table with a magnitude of 1.660 so it can be concluded that the value of t-count ($8.800 > t\text{-table} (1.660)$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that hypothesis 1 "brand image has a positive effect on purchasing decisions (Y)" is accepted.

Based on the calculations from Table 5, it is found that the t-count of the e-service quality variable is 12.201. Furthermore, the value of the t-table is searched through the previous df (degree of freedom), so that $df = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$ is obtained. The df is obtained as much as 98, then if observed through t-one tailed using 5% significance, the value will be obtained t table with a magnitude of 1.660 so it can be concluded that the value of t-count ($12.201 > t\text{-table} (1.660)$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that hypothesis 2 "e-service quality has a positive effect on purchasing decisions (Y)" is accepted.

Based on the calculations from Table 6, it is found that the t-count of the customer value variable is 10.236. Furthermore, the value of the t-table is searched through the previous df (degree of freedom), so that $df = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$ is obtained. The df is obtained as much as 98, then if observed through t-one tailed using 5% significance, the value will be obtained t table with a magnitude of 1.660 so it can be concluded that the value of t-count ($10.236 > t\text{-table} (1.660)$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that hypothesis 3 "customer value has a positive effect on purchasing decisions (Y)" is accepted.

F-test

Table 11. Calculated F Test Results between Brand Image, E-Service Quality, and Customer Value on Purchase Decisions

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	465.830	3	155.277	62.588	.000 ^b
	Residual	238.170	96	2.481		
	Total	704.000	99			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Value, Brand Image, E-Service Quality

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on the calculations in Table 11, it is known that the calculation results from the F value are 62.588 and the f-table value is searched through the previous df (degree of freedom), so that we get $df = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$. Obtaining df as much as 98, then if observed through the t-one tail using a significance of 5%, the t-table value will be obtained with a magnitude of 2.697. From the results of these calculations, it is shown that the calculated F value (62.588) > F table value (2.697), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that hypothesis 4 "there is a positive influence between brand image, e-service quality, and customer value on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results show that the brand image variable has a positive influence on the decision to use services at Traveloka in Semarang City. This situation can be seen from the results of the study which explains that the relationship between the brand image variable and purchasing decisions is stated to be strong because it has a correlation coefficient value of 0.687 where this value is in the interval range of 0.60 - 0.799. Furthermore, the results of testing the coefficient of determination between brand image and purchasing decisions produce an R^2 value of 0.441 or 44.1%, meaning that there is 44.1% of the purchasing decision variables contributing to the influence of the brand image variable, while the remaining 55.9% is explained by the variable others that were not studied in this study. Based on the calculation of the t test, the results obtained t count is 8,800 > t table which is 1,660 then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so that hypothesis 1, namely "there is a positive influence between brand image on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

In addition, it is known that the e-service quality variable has a positive effect on the decision to use services at Traveloka in Semarang City. This situation can be seen from the results of the study which show that the relationship between the e-service quality variable and purchasing decisions is included in the strong category because it has a correlation coefficient value of 0.777 where this value is in the interval range of 0.60 - 0.799. Furthermore, the results of the calculation of the coefficient of determination between e-service quality and purchasing decisions that produce an R^2 value of 0.603 or 60.3%, meaning that there are 60.3% of the purchasing decision variables contributed to the influence of the e-service quality variable, while the remaining 39, 7% is explained by other variables not examined in this study. As for the results of the calculations on the t test, the results obtained where the value of t count (12.201) > t table value (1.660) then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so that hypothesis 2, namely "there is a positive influence between e-service quality on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

In addition to brand image and e-service quality, it is found that the customer value variable has a positive influence on the decision to use services at Traveloka in Semarang City. This situation can be seen from the results of the study which explains that the relationship between the variable customer value and purchasing decisions is declared strong because it has a correlation coefficient value of 0.687 where this value is in the interval range of 0.60 - 0.799. Furthermore, the results of testing the coefficient of determination between brand image and purchasing decisions resulted in an R^2 value of 0.517 or 51.7%, meaning that there was 51.7% of the purchasing decision variables contributed to the influence of the customer value variable, while the remaining 48.3% was explained by the variable others that were not studied in this study. Based on the t-test calculation, the results obtained by t-count are 10.236 > t-table which is 1.660, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so hypothesis 3, namely "there is a positive influence between customer value on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

This study also found that the variables of brand image, e-service quality, and customer value had a positive effect on purchasing decisions. This is evidenced by the results of the analysis which shows that the relationship between brand image, e-service quality, and customer value with purchasing decisions is included in the very strong category because it has a correlation coefficient value of 0.813 where this value is in the interval 0.80 - 1,000. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination of brand image, e-service quality, and customer value on purchasing decisions is 0.662 or 66.2%, meaning that there are as many as 66.2% of the purchasing decision variables contributing to the influence of the brand image variable, e-service quality, and customer value, while the remaining 33.8% is explained by other variables not examined in this study. As for the results of the calculations on the t test, the results obtained where the calculated F value is 62.588 > the F table value is 2.697, so that it can be concluded that hypothesis 4, namely "brand image, e-service quality, and customer value have a positive effect on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been carried out, it is known that the brand image variable (X1) has a strong, positive, and significant influence on purchasing decisions. The brand image obtained from using Traveloka is good, but there are several things that need to be considered, such as the appearance of a crowded design and inappropriate feature placement, or problems with changing schedules. Overall, brand image can encourage Traveloka users in Semarang City to make purchases.

Based on this research, it was found that the e-service quality variable (X2) has a strong, positive, and significant influence on the purchasing decision variable. E-service quality related to Traveloka is considered good, but there are several things to be improved later, such as the difficulty of transacting when using Traveloka, the system sometimes does not respond and then the application closes by itself. In addition, customer service is less responsive and does not provide a good solution to the problem. Overall, e-service quality can encourage Traveloka users in Semarang City to make purchases.

In addition to brand image and e-service quality, it is found that the customer value variable (X3) has a strong, positive, and significant influence on the purchasing decision variable. E-service quality related to Traveloka is considered good, but there are several things to be improved later, such as shopping (purchase) at Traveloka sometimes not worth the benefits obtained, the recommendations displayed are sometimes inappropriate, and the Traveloka party is not responsive and the Traveloka system the error causes users to label Traveloka badly. Overall, customer value can encourage Traveloka users in Semarang City to make purchases.

Based on the results of this study, the results show that the brand image (X1), e-service quality (X2), and customer value (X3) variables together have a strong, positive, and significant influence on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The better the brand image, e-service quality, and customer value variables will encourage Traveloka users in Semarang City to purchase tickets or hotel reservations.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the research, it is shown that Traveloka's brand image is quite good, but there are still a number of things that are important to be maintained and improved. The Traveloka company is advised to consistently embed the tagline in every ad content created, improve the platform design, and optimize the schedule change feature, both on the website and application. When users feel comfortable in making purchases at Traveloka, later users will be encouraged to provide positive reviews regarding the Traveloka brand image.

Based on the results of the research, it is shown that Traveloka's e-service quality is quite good, but there are still a number of things that are important to maintain and improve. Traveloka companies are advised to consistently direct technicians and teams to optimize Traveloka digital domains and control as soon as possible if errors and inaccuracies occur in service functions, optimize services for user complaints and provide quick responses, and provide training, direction, and attention to customer service so that they can able to provide the best service.

Based on the research results, it is shown that Traveloka's customer value is quite good, but there are still a number of things that are important to be maintained and improved. Traveloka companies are advised to maximize platform performance and increase rewards and promo options to provide a pleasant experience. The Traveloka company is advised to continue to optimize and improve the completeness of features and quality of service intensively so that the benefits (results) obtained by buyers/users are in accordance with the efforts and costs incurred. Traveloka companies are advised to continue to provide maximum service, create the best value, improve customer experience, and provide benefits to customers.

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